

Colon cancer patient cases (diagnosis images and clinical data) for the training and validation of AI models

ID: 4a97e985-ecdb-4ed2-9ed9-a8917dc6ceb8

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/4a97e985-ecdb-4ed2-9ed9-a8917dc6ceb8/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 904

Subjects count: 904

Age range: Between 28 years and 97 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): ABDOMEN, CHEST, COLOSCANNER, TAP, BRAIN, NECK, LUNG, COLOSCANNER EAU, SPINE, WHOLEBODY, TORAX, TXABDPELVIS, ABDOMEN / PELVIS, ABDOPELV, CRANE COLO, THORAX, TC ABD_MINO_P_LV, EXTREMITY, AORTA, TXABDOMENPELVIS, CTAP, UROSCANNER, CAP, Unknown

Modality: CT, DX, PT